

**TEACHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS AND CHALLENGES OF TEACHING
LEARNING, EXTENSION AND RESEARCH ACTIVITY**

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic is considered as the most crucial global health calamity of the century and the greatest challenge that the humankind faced since the 2nd World War. In December 2019, a new infectious respiratory disease emerged in Wuhan, Hubei province, China and was named by the World Health Organization as COVID-19 (coronavirus disease 2019). A new class of corona virus, known as SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2) has been found to be responsible for occurrence of this disease. As far as the history of human civilization is concerned there are instances of severe outbreaks of diseases caused by a number of viruses. According to the report of the World Health Organization (WHO as of April 18 2020), the current outbreak of COVID-19, has affected over 2164111 people and killed more than 146,198 people in more than 200 countries throughout the world. Till now there is no report of any clinically approved antiviral drugs or vaccines that are effective against COVID-19. It has rapidly spread around the world, posing enormous health, economic, environmental and social challenges to the entire human population. The coronavirus outbreak is severely disrupting the global economy. Almost all the nations are struggling to slow down the transmission of the disease by testing & treating patients, quarantining suspected persons through contact tracing, restricting large gatherings, maintaining complete or partial lock down etc. This paper describes the impact of COVID-19 epidemic on college of education who offers degree course and challenges of teacher student relationship in teaching learning ,extension and research activity, and the possible ways in which the problem can be resolved has also been discussed therein.

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KEY WORDS – Pandemic Ugc Ncte College Of Education Cbcs

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic is considered as the most crucial global health calamity of the century and the greatest challenge that the humankind faced since the 2nd World War. In December 2019, a new infectious respiratory disease emerged in Wuhan, Hubei province, China and was named by the World Health Organization as COVID-19 (coronavirus disease 2019). A new class of corona virus, known as

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Such circumstances created some issues before higher education institutions

CHALLENGES BEFORE HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS/UNIVERSITIES IN COVID -19 PANDEMIC

1. If students are unable to return to campus this fall, colleges and universities could face unanticipated and historic attrition from students who are either unsatisfied with their distance-learning experience or whose ability to afford tuition in the current economic climate will be inhibited; others may simply decide to stay closer to home in uncertain times. Even well-resourced institutions will find it hard to forecast enrollment for the 2020–21 academic year
2. For institutions that were already financially stressed or operating from a deficit position prior to the pandemic, short-term unanticipated expenses and longer-term enrollment declines will likely threaten their solvency, potentially forcing numerous closures and mergers. Here we explore some key considerations for colleges and universities as they find their fiscal footing in a very different operating environment in the months ahead. The coronavirus pandemic has upended business as usual for colleges and universities. Not only have campuses shifted to remote learning almost overnight, but institutions are also suddenly grappling with grave financial challenges as the domestic and global economies may now face what looks to be a major recession.
3. The most immediate challenge for most institutions involves cash flow. As institutions lose parking fees, dining outlet sales, and other auxiliary revenues, they also face unexpected expenses, including partial refunds on fees, room, and board, and the need to scale virtual engagement modalities. To ensure continuity in the short term, some institutions will likely need to rapidly restructure their operations.

HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA-ITS EXPETATIONS

The National Policy on Higher Education (1986) translated the vision of the Radhakrishnan Commission and the Kothari Commission into an actionable policy by setting five main goals for higher education, as enumerated below:

- **Access:** Greater access requires an enhancement of the education institutional capacity of the higher education sector to provide opportunities to all those who deserve and desire higher education.
- **Equity:** Equity involves fair access of the poor and the socially disadvantaged groups to higher education.
- **Quality and Excellence:** involve provision of education in accordance with accepted standards so that students receive available knowledge of the highest standard that helps them to enhance their human resource capabilities.
- **Relevance:** involves promotion of education so as to develop human resources keeping pace with the changing economic, social and cultural development of the country; and
- **Value Based Education:** involves inculcating basic moral values among the y D1.1.1 Objectives The XI as well as the XII Plan have laid emphasis on improving access, equity and excellence. The XII Plan mentions that access must be increased, preferably through consolidation of existing institutions and special importance is to be given to excellence or quality

TEACHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS –ROLE OF NCTE

The National Council for Teacher Education is a statutory body set up under the National Council for Teacher Education Act, 1993 to facilitate planned and coordinated development of the teacher education system in the country, and for regulation and proper maintenance of norms and standards in the teacher education system. The mandate given to the NCTE is very broad and covers the whole gamut of teacher education programs including research and training of persons to equip them to teach at pre-primary, primary, secondary and senior secondary stages in schools, and non-formal education, part-time education, adult education and distance (correspondence) education courses. The Council, under Section 12 is responsible for the following activities and functions:

- i. to coordinate and monitor teacher education and its development in the country;
- ii. lay down guidelines in respect of minimum qualifications for a person to be employed as a teacher;
- iii. lay down norms for any specified category of courses or trainings in teacher education;
- iv. lay down guidelines for compliance by recognized institutions for starting new courses or training;
- v. lay down standards in respect of examinations, leading to teacher education qualifications, and
- vi. examine and review periodically the implementation of the norms, guidelines and standards laid down by the Council.

The Council is empowered to grant recognition of institutions offering courses or training in teacher education

PRESENT CURRICULUM STRUCTURE OF COLLEGE OF EDUCATION

So far concern with Swami Ramanand Tirth Marathwada University, Nanded is reframed the curriculum of B.Ed programme and the course duration is of two year. In the CBCS (CHOICE BASED CREDIT SYSTEM) learning system the minimum instructional days for semester pattern is of 100-105

workingdays. One credit of 15 contact hours for theory courses and 30 hours for internal .one credit equals to 25 marks credit points. Evaluation system will be continuous internal assessment and the weightage for end semester assessment is 44% and 56% for continuous internal assessment

The Programme structure offers a comprehensive coverage of themes and rigorous fields engagement with the child, school and community. It comprises of three broad interrelated curricular areas prescribed by NCT.

1. Perspective in education
2. Curriculum and Pedagogic studies
3. Engagement with the Field.

PROBLEMS AND REMEDIES

For B.Ed course common entrance is conducted by state every year s and students gets admitted therein. Delay in admission, student poor response for the course, average students admission , mushroom growth of teacher training institutions, teacher student ratio is very poor, span of semester and the time for field work is very less, attitude of student , private management and their attitude, Engagement with field maintaining social distance were some experienced problems. Covid 19 may severe it .

1. Teacher education in India to be brought in line with and at the frontiers of global trends in higher education and knowledge development, the task seems very difficult in present scenario.
2. Improvement in the overall quality of teaching-learning in an average teacher education institution in the country in the present time is quite difficult
3. Arresting and reversing the trend of group inequalities in access to quality higher education is now major task

REMEDIES

Restructuring Semester pattern, optimum use of online teaching , use interactive teaching learning process, quality based home assignment, full time teacher role so as to get the vivid experience of teaching field rather than internship to the student , home assignment for theory and school for all practicum the only solution for all problems. School should pay some incentive for the trainee teacher so the economical problem will solve upto certain extent. The internal evaluation is of online nature and continuous one . The overall planning and management responsibility is of training institute and the teaching staff will coordinate all related one.

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